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DIATOMIC: Exploring Worldwide 3D City-scale Models

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Abstract

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Three-dimensional (3D) city-scale models are growing in popularity worldwide, driven by their applications in urban planning, infrastructure analysis, and disaster management. The appropriate model type and level of detail depend heavily on the intended use-case; in some scenarios, two-dimensional (2D) models remain a suitable and more cost-effective alternative.

This report examines the key differences between 2D and 3D city-scale models, reviews the methodologies used to create 3D models, and explores how these models are applied across different cities globally. Where an indoor focus and high geometric detail are required, a Level of Detail 4 (LoD4) approach is most appropriate, while hybrid methodologies – combining LiDAR data with satellite imagery – are better suited to broad, city-wide perspectives.

To inform best practice, this report analyses and compares existing 3D city models from Hamburg, Helsinki, Rotterdam, London, Singapore, and New York, providing a foundation for the development of future 3D city-scale models.

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Introduction

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Introduction

A three-dimensional (3D) city model should enhance the understanding and visualisation of buildings, infrastructure, and the wider urban ecosystem, ultimately enabling more efficient planning and decision-making. Such models can vary significantly depending on the city and its built environment, the intended purpose of the model, and the methodology used to create it. This report explores existing 3D city models from cities around the world, examining the methodologies and purposes behind each to identify areas of best practice.

While 3D models exist across multiple continents, this report focuses on examples from Hamburg, Helsinki, Rotterdam, London, Singapore and New York.

1.1 What is a 3D City Model?

A 3D city-scale model is a digital representation of a city, encompassing urban and suburban environments and potentially extending to rural areas^{1,2,3}. These models can be designed to varying levels of detail, capturing terrain, vegetation, building features, bodies of water, and transport systems^{3,4}. They may represent individual buildings or features intended for integration into larger models, or they may cover an entire city landscape³.

Singh et al.¹ identifies three primary geomatic approaches to creating a 3D city-scale model: using vector map data or aerial imagery; using high-resolution satellite images; and using terrestrial images alongside digital surface models and texture mapping.

It is worth noting that while 3D city-scale models can support digital twin development by providing a visual component⁵, a 3D model or visualisation alone – without real-time data integration and simulation capabilities – does not constitute a digital twin.

1.2 3D Models versus Two-Dimensional (2D) Models

Historically, 2D city models using geographic information systems (GIS) have been the standard for urban planning⁶ and remain the dominant form of geographical mapping today. They are less costly and time-consuming to produce than 3D alternatives and typically display a city from above on a single horizontal plane – an orthographic, or plan view, projection.

The availability and affordability of 2D data has improved considerably in recent decades. The European Space Agency's IKONOS satellite⁷, launched in the early 2000s, was one of the first publicly available high-resolution data sources, offering up to one-metre resolution at a cost of up to \$200 per square kilometre, with an additional \$3,000 charge for expedited access⁸. By contrast, a 50 square kilometre image is now priced at approximately \$8 per square kilometre⁹ – a dramatic reduction. Despite this increased affordability, the quality difference between 2D and 3D data remains significant.

AI is increasingly enabling the automated conversion of 2D imagery into 3D models¹⁰. However, higher-detail outputs – such as LoD3 and LoD4 models – continue to require a largely manual approach, demanding considerable time and cost¹¹. Even where some degree of automation is possible for LoD3, scalability remains a notable challenge¹².

2D models are well-suited to use-cases that do not require information about building height or three-dimensional spatial relationships. Many users are now digitally familiar with plan-view mapping through everyday tools such as mobile navigation apps. This format works particularly well for basic distance measurement and in flatter terrains with little elevation change¹³. Practical examples include navigation tools with overlaid routes¹³, boundary and zone plotting¹⁴, and traffic dashboards displaying volume, bicycle counts, and collision data¹⁵ – none of which require the additional dimension that a 3D model provides.

Where building height, depth, and spatial relationships do matter, however, 3D models offer clear advantages⁶. Shadow and sight-line analysis, solar panel placement optimisation¹⁶, noise and air pollution modelling¹⁷, and disaster mitigation planning for events such as floods, fires, or explosions¹⁷ can all benefit significantly from the additional detail a 3D model provides. By integrating topography, zoning, building

'AI is increasingly enabling the automated conversion of 2D imagery into 3D models.'

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'3D city models make urban planning more approachable and effective than traditional 2D approaches.'

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facades, and environmental factors, 3D models give urban planners a far richer basis for analysis and decision-making¹⁵.

1.3 Use Cases for 3D City Models

3D city models serve a wide range of purposes, spanning urban planning, disaster management, tourism, navigation, and telecommunications.

When city models first began transitioning from 2D GIS to 3D, the primary motivation was improved visualisation^{18,19}. As the technology has advanced, so too has demand for these models to deliver broader analytical functionality. Zhang et al.²⁰ note that the spatial analysis capabilities of 3D city models make urban planning more approachable and effective than traditional 2D approaches.

Two frameworks for categorising 3D model use-cases are relevant here. Biljecki et al.¹⁸ organises use-cases into visualisation and non-visualisation categories, identifying 29 distinct applications (24 visualisation, 5 non-visualisation). Chen²¹, by contrast, groups use-cases into five broader categories: urban planning, disaster management, tourism, navigation, and telecommunication. Both frameworks are complementary – the five categories of Chen²¹ can each accommodate specific use-cases from Biljecki et al.¹⁸, such as building classification, flood modelling, lighting simulation, navigation visualisation, and radio-wave propagation.

Ultimately, the appropriate use-case framework depends on the specific needs of the user and the context in which the model will be deployed. Different cities and countries have developed their 3D models in response to different priorities, and the output of any model should be understood relative to its intended purpose. The following section explores a range of models from cities across the world, each reflecting their own use-case requirements.

References

¹⁸ [Link](#)

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When creating a 3D city model, both international and community standards play an important role in ensuring that different methods and datasets can be integrated effectively, and that the resulting models are broadly accessible and interpretable by users.

2.1 Data Standards and Formats

Several data standards and formats have been established within the field of 3D city modelling to facilitate interoperability and simplify the integration of diverse datasets. The most widely adopted international standard is CityGML, which defines a conceptual model and exchange format for the representation, storage, and sharing of virtual 3D city models²². While CityGML models may contain less detail than some alternatives, they typically cover larger spatial areas and are structured around five standardised Levels of Detail (LoD): LoD0 through to LoD4²³. At LoD0, buildings are represented by footprints in what is essentially a 2D visualisation; at LoD4, models include interior features such as rooms and building openings, representing the highest level of geometric and semantic detail²⁴. The choice of LoD should reflect the intended use of the model – a low LoD may be insufficient for many complex urban planning applications, while LoD4 detail may be unnecessary unless interior representation is specifically required²⁵. CityJSON is a related standard that implements a subset of the CityGML data model using a JSON-based format. CityJSON is published by the Open Geospatial Consortium as a community standard, developed and maintained by practitioners and therefore does not carry the same level of formal institutional endorsement as CityGML, which is a fully ratified international standard²⁶. It was designed with developer accessibility in mind, making it easier to integrate with APIs and software applications, and well-suited to web and mobile platforms²⁷. A further community standard is 3D Tiles, which is also derived from CityGML. Designed for the efficient rendering and streaming of large 3D spatial datasets including photogrammetric outputs and point clouds; 3D Tiles achieves this through a hierarchical data structure and a set of tile formats that support renderable content²⁸. Alongside these technical standards, data security and privacy are increasingly important considerations in the creation and sharing of 3D city models. High-resolution models, particularly those developed to LoD3 or LoD4, can reveal sensitive information such as detailed building layouts, infrastructure assets, and indicators of how buildings are used or occupied. For this reason, access controls, data anonymisation, and compliance with relevant data protection legislation must be considered at every stage of the data lifecycle, from initial collection through to publication and reuse. Without these safeguards, detailed 3D data can be misused or combined with other datasets in ways that expose sensitive or personal information. Where datasets incorporate personal data such as occupancy information, addresses linked to identifiable individuals, compliance with the UK General Data Protection Regulation (UK GDPR) and the Data Protection Act 2018 must be considered. Details about critical infrastructure should be handled in accordance with relevant national security guidance, with appropriate access controls applied to mitigate the risk of sensitive asset information being misused or publicly exposed. Local authorities and regional bodies such as the West Midlands Combined Authority (WMCA) may therefore need to apply measures such as restricted access, data aggregation, or reduced geometric and texture detail. These approaches help to manage privacy and security risks while still enabling the data to support effective urban planning, analysis, and decision-making.

‘... access controls, data anonymisation, and compliance with relevant data protection legislation must be considered at every stage.’

2.2 Modelling Guides

A key reference for best practice in 3D city-scale modelling is the guide produced by SIG3D²⁹. This guide comprises two parts: Part 1 covers the foundational rules for using and validating GML geometries in CityGML³⁰, while Part 2 provides a more detailed treatment of building modelling across three levels of detail – LoD1, LoD2, and LoD3³¹. The guide focuses on the modelling of individual building types within a city, rather than the creation of a complete city model. It draws on national German and European standards throughout, and assumes working knowledge of GML (Geography Markup Language), CityGML, and ALKIS (the Official German Land Registry Information System)³¹.

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SIG3D is also developing a companion Testing Guide²⁹, which sets out requirements that a 3D city model must meet depending on its intended purpose. For example, a model designed for visualisation will have different requirements to one intended for energy calculations, and this guide provides a framework for testing whether those respective requirements have been satisfied²⁹.

2.3 Levels of Detail

As noted in Section 2.1, 3D city models can be created to five levels of detail, LoD0 through to LoD4 with the complexity and geometric fidelity of the model increasing at each level²⁴.

Figure 1 illustrates the five levels and the degree of detail each provides. LoD0 is the least detailed level, representing buildings as footprints draped over a terrain surface. This is sometimes referred to as 2.5D – meaning that while elevation data is present, the model cannot represent overhanging structures or multiple surfaces at the same horizontal position, falling short of true three-dimensional representation. LoD1 represents buildings as simple extruded blocks, accurate to their footprint and assigned a uniform height, but without reflecting the actual shape, roof form, or facade variation of the building. LoD2 introduces differentiated roof geometry, capturing the actual roof form of each building alongside basic facade surfaces, while LoD3 extends this further by adding architectural openings such as doors and windows, producing an accurate representation of the building's exterior. LoD4 is the most detailed level, incorporating interior architectural elements such as rooms, staircases, and interior doors and windows, enabling the model to represent the internal structure of a building as well as its exterior²⁴. As with all modelling decisions, the appropriate level of detail should be determined by the intended use-case.

Figure 1

The five different Levels of Detail, defined by CityGML²⁴.

2.4 Hybrid Methodologies

A hybrid methodology combines two or more techniques to create a 3D city model, typically by enhancing an existing 2D approach with additional three-dimensional data. Common examples include combining GIS software with digitised maps, or merging satellite data with ground surveys³². LiDAR data and photogrammetry can also be used in combination to produce accurate 3D outputs³³.

Building Information Modelling (BIM) represents a further hybrid approach. BIM involves the digital recreation and representation of buildings using structured data, with each model composed of BIM objects, three-dimensional representations of buildings and other physical elements, populated with relevant attribute information³⁴.

BIM implementation is typically described across four maturity levels, from Level 0 to Level 3, reflecting the increasing sophistication of digital working practices, data management, and collaborative processes. At Level 0, BIM has not yet been adopted and only unmanaged 2D drawings exist, with no collaboration between professional disciplines such as architects, structural engineers, mechanical and electrical engineers, and contractors. Level 1 introduces managed CAD in either 2D or 3D format, though each discipline continues to work independently. Level 2 involves collaborative working through federated 3D models, where each discipline maintains its own model and coordinates with others. Level 3 represents full integration, with all disciplines working within a single shared model environment³⁴. 3D point cloud data can also be used as a basis for generating BIM models³⁵.

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'It is important that the quality of a model is understood in relation to the freshness of its data and its capacity to reflect ongoing changes in the urban environment.'

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2.5 Accuracy and Temporal Validity of Data

Given the constantly evolving nature of urban environments, the temporal validity and therefore the accuracy of any 3D city model must be carefully considered. Cities change continuously, with buildings constructed or demolished, infrastructure updated, and land use modified over time. Models that rely on infrequent aerial surveys or static datasets risk becoming outdated, potentially undermining their reliability for planning or analytical purposes. The temporal currency of the underlying data is therefore a fundamental determinant of model quality, and any outdated data within a 3D city model will have a direct and significant impact on its usefulness^{36,37}.

It is important that the quality of a model is understood in relation to the freshness of its data and its capacity to reflect ongoing changes in the urban environment. This should be a key consideration when assessing the reliability of any 3D city model. Clearly acknowledging and documenting any data uncertainties is equally important, ensuring that planners and decision-makers can use the model appropriately and avoid misinterpreting information that may no longer accurately reflect current conditions.

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Worldwide 3D City-scale Model Examples

This section examines 3D city models created by cities across the world, identifying the methodologies and use-cases behind each where possible. The cities discussed are Hamburg, Helsinki, Rotterdam, London, Singapore, and New York.

3.1 Hamburg

A notable example from Germany is the 3D city model of Hamburg, created by the State Office for Geoinformation and Surveying (SOGS)³⁸. This model is built to Level of Detail 3 (LoD3), with building textures generated from oblique aerial imagery – photographs taken at an angle rather than directly overhead – at a resolution of 20 cm, in accordance with data protection requirements³⁸. The model supports the overlay of more than 500 data layers, ranging from educational and sporting facilities to heating network coverage and bus lane locations across the city³⁹. [Figure 2](#) shows a portion of the Hamburg model. The LoD3 approach enables individual buildings to be clearly distinguished from one another; Hamburg Cathedral and Hamburg Town Hall, for example, are readily identifiable within the model. [Figure 3](#) illustrates several data layers overlaid onto the LoD3 model, including bus lanes (shown as blue lines), buildings connected to the heating network (shown as red boxes)³⁹. The ability to overlay more than 500 separate data layers makes this model a powerful tool for urban understanding and planning.

Figure 2
Part of the Hamburg 3D city model³⁸.

Figure 3
Screenshot of the Hamburg 3D city model, highlighting different data layers³⁹.

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3.2 Helsinki

3.2.1 3D Mesh Model

The City of Helsinki, a government organisation, has produced a 3D mesh model of the city⁴⁰. This was created by processing aerial photographs through an application that transforms the images into a triangulated mesh texture. The accuracy of the model is therefore dependent on the quality of the source imagery; areas containing reflective surfaces or moving objects may not be represented with full accuracy. [Figure 4](#) shows the Helsinki mesh model at a broad scale, capturing a large portion of the city centre. Due to the nature of combining multiple aerial images, and the constant movement of water surfaces compared to static buildings, water areas are visually less accurate than the urban portions of the model. Within the urban area, however, accuracy is considerably higher, with the exception of objects that were reflecting light or in motion during image capture. The City of Helsinki describes this model as suited to design or network service applications, or for use on game engine platforms, where its capacity to measure volume, elevation differences, and surface areas can be effectively utilised⁴⁰.

Figure 4

Overview of a Helsinki 3D City Model⁴¹.

‘The Urban Data Model provides a more detailed view of the buildings and terrain captured in the Helsinki mesh model.’

3.2.2 Urban Data Model

The Urban Data Model provides a more detailed view of the buildings and terrain captured in the Helsinki mesh model. It records building characteristics including construction year, number of floors, address, and building type and classification, and can be viewed in either an OpenStreetMap or aerial view⁴⁰. The model was created by combining laser scanning, aerial photographs, and building data models to produce a 3D output from merged terrain and surface models. It is updated regularly, both to add further detail to existing buildings and to accurately reflect ongoing changes in the urban landscape⁴⁰.

[Figure 5](#) shows the building characteristics displayed for a selected structure within the Urban Data Model. The ability to access an interactive 3D city model with embedded urban data is of considerable value, providing both the geometry and key attributes of buildings across the city for a wide range of use-cases. Building geometries within the Urban Data Model incorporate a mixture of LoD1 (flat roofs) and LoD2 (differentiated roof forms), with each building represented using Semantic CityGML objects.

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Figure 5

Example of the data seen in the Helsinki Urban Data Model⁴¹.

3.3 Rotterdam

The Government of Rotterdam (Gemeente Rotterdam) offers a freely accessible 3D city model titled Rotterdam 3D⁴². The model was created by combining 2D maps, height measurements, LiDAR data, aerial photographs, and land survey data of street-level objects to produce an accurate 3D representation of the city. Cesium 3D Tiles⁴² are used to render the complex geometries of the urban environment.

Figure 6 shows an overview of the interactive Rotterdam 3D model, in which walls are depicted in grey and roofs in red, making individual buildings readily distinguishable from one another. Figure 7 shows a selected building, Rotterdam Centraal Station, along with its associated building characteristics including location, address, and number of floors, comparable to the data seen in Figure 5.

One notable feature embedded within the Rotterdam 3D model is a shadow analysis tool, which simulates the shadows cast by each building for any specified date and time⁴³. This functionality is particularly valuable for infrastructure planning, enabling users to understand how shadows fall across the city at different times of day and year. Alongside this, the Rotterdam 3D model supports many of the broader use-cases discussed in Section 1.3.

Figure 6

Section of Rotterdam 3D City Model⁴³.

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Figure 7

Building Data for Rotterdam Centraal Station⁴³.

Worldwide 3D City-scale Model Examples continued

'... including Education Establishments, Air Pollution, Flood Defences, Listed Land, EPC Ratings, and Biodiversity Hotspots.'

3.4 London

A 3D city model of London has been created by VU.CITY, covering all 1,619 square kilometres of the city to an accuracy of 15 cm. The model contains 3.3 million buildings and more than 10 million trees, each represented at the correct height and canopy size, felt to make one of the largest 3D city-scale models in the world⁴⁴. It supports 290 data layers, including Education Establishments, Air Pollution, Flood Defences, Listed Land, EPC Ratings, and Biodiversity Hotspots⁴⁴.

VU.CITY offer models across four levels of detail – LoD1, LoD2, LoD3, and LoD4. Based on the level of detail visible in the London model, it is understood to be predominantly LoD3, with select areas such as Canary Wharf and sports stadiums enhanced to LoD4.

Figures 8, 9, and 10 illustrate a selection of the 290 data layers available within the model, giving a strong indication of its scale and quality. The combination of high LoD geometry with an extensive range of potential data layers to be overlaid makes this a powerful resource for urban exploration, planning, and analysis.

Figure 8

View of the London 3D Model, highlighting flood defences⁴⁴.

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Figure 9

View of the London 3D Model, highlighting listed land⁴⁴.

Figure 10

View of the London 3D Model, highlighting different domestic EPC ratings⁴⁴.

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3.5 Singapore

In Singapore, a 3D model created by the company Vizzio covers the entire country at a 1:1 scale, comprising 728 million square metre tiles⁴⁵. The model was constructed through the amalgamation of thousands of satellite images, processed using 3D modelling technology to produce a detailed reconstruction. Real-time data collection via drones, sensors, and other tools can be integrated on top of the base model to keep it current⁴⁵.

Figure 11 shows the Vizzio model of Singapore. The use of satellite imagery produces ground colours that appear more photorealistic than those generated through an LoD-based approach, as seen in Section 3.4. However, this method does not achieve the same level of individual building detail as an LoD model.

Vizzio are developing a metaverse version of Singapore, intended for both recreational use and, more prominently, gamification purposes. Figure 12 highlights the quality of the model that will underpin this metaverse environment.

Figure 11

View of the Singapore 3D city model, created by Vizzio⁴⁶.

Figure 12

Different images of the Singapore 3D Model, that will be used for the creation of a metaverse⁴⁵.

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'... data layers encompassing air pollution, energy performance, zoning districts, and bicycle routes.'

Worldwide 3D City-scale Model Examples continued

3.6 New York

A 3D model of New York has also been produced by VU.CITY, the same company responsible for the London model discussed in Section 3.4. This model covers 116 square kilometres of the city to an accuracy of 15 cm, and includes 16 data layers encompassing air pollution, energy performance, zoning districts, and bicycle routes⁴⁷.

Figures 13 and 14 demonstrate the model's quality and its capacity to display overlaid data effectively. The model is completed to LoD3, with building facades accurately represented across the city. In addition to the 16 data layers, the model supports sunlight and shadow analysis, as well as theoretical visibility zone mapping. These capabilities, combined with the data layers and the scale of the model, provide a strong foundation for urban planning and development within New York City.

Several other 3D city models exist for New York, though these tend to be more commercially focused with limited public access. One example is CityZenith⁴⁸, whose model is developed around a Clean Cities – Clean Future framework⁴⁹.

Figure 13

View of the New York city model by VU.CITY, highlighting building energy performance⁴⁷.

Figure 14

View of the New York city model by VU.CITY, highlighting the zoning districts⁴⁷.

References

- ⁴⁷ [Link](#)
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'Access to an appropriate 3D city model can enable much easier and more detailed urban planning across the city.'

Conclusion: Recommending a 3D Model

Drawing on the methods, outputs, and use-cases observed across 3D city models from around the world, this section offers insights to inform the creation of a suitable model.

4.1 Reasons to Create a 3D Model

The motivations for creating a 3D city model are varied, and clearly identifying these is the essential first step in the process. Once the purpose of the model has been established, the desired output can be defined, and decisions about model type and methodology can follow from there. Access to an appropriate 3D city model can significantly enhance urban planning, support the assessment of potential disaster impacts, and provide a richer understanding of the city across a broad range of applications.

However, whilst the benefits of 3D city models are substantial, the computational cost and accessibility of these models must also be taken into account. High-resolution models require significant processing power, storage capacity, and specialised software, which can limit accessibility for smaller organisations or public users. There are therefore notable trade-offs between performance, visual quality, and ease of access that must be carefully weighed when scoping any new model.

4.2 Existing 3D Models

Examining existing models from across the world reveals a wide variety of methodologies and outputs, each reflecting the specific use-cases or preferences of the organisation responsible for its creation. Two primary approaches emerge from the models reviewed in this report: Level of Detail modelling, applied at varying degrees of detail, and satellite imagery-based modelling, in which imagery is processed and combined with modelling tools to construct a 3D output.

Helsinki illustrates both approaches – an overhead mesh model created from satellite imagery, and a more detailed Urban Data Model produced using a Level of Detail approach. The LoD-based models reviewed in this report have generally gone further by embedding relevant data within individual buildings and supporting the overlay of additional data layers. Rotterdam and Singapore, both of which used satellite imagery as the primary data source, offer a broader city-wide perspective and represent building facades with photorealistic accuracy, but do not achieve the same level of per-building detail as the LoD-based models.

4.3 Suitable Methodology for Use-Cases

The choice between these two approaches should be determined by the intended outcome of the model. Where the primary goal is a useful city-wide overview – supporting sight line analysis and the overlay of data onto the model – a satellite imagery approach combined with 3D modelling tools is most appropriate. Where the goal is to store and interrogate data within individual buildings, a block-based Level of Detail approach is better suited.

The appropriate Level of Detail should similarly be determined by the intended use-case. LoD0 is not recommended, as it lacks meaningful 3D properties. LoD1 provides the minimum block-level quality for a 3D model but is insufficient for most realistic applications and is therefore not recommended for more complex use. LoD2 offers a more realistic representation of the urban landscape and building forms, enabling users to visually appreciate the chosen area, and is used within the Helsinki Urban Data Model discussed in Section 3.2.2. While LoD2 is suitable for some 3D modelling purposes, it lacks the visual detail provided by LoD3 and LoD4, both of which significantly increase the quality and utility of the model. LoD3 seems to be the most widely used level across the city models reviewed in this report, including Hamburg, London, and New York as it delivers a high level of visual detail and supports meaningful data interactivity at the level of individual buildings, making it suitable for the majority of use-cases. LoD4 provides the greatest level of building detail, extending representation to the interior of structures. This level is recommended where use-cases require precise interior measurements or an understanding of internal layouts, as is typically the case in the construction and planning sector.

Conclusion: Recommending a 3D Model continued

To conclude, the most suitable approach for creating a 3D city model that meets the standard required for visual understanding and appreciation of the city, whilst supporting data layer interactivity throughout, is Level of Detail 3. In certain cases, an upgrade to Level of Detail 4 may be necessary, though this should be determined on a case-by-case basis according to the specific requirements of the use-case.

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All weblinks were accessed over Q3 2025 and Q1 2026 unless otherwise specified.

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